

A Kinetic Study of Alkaline Hydrolysis of Methyl Nicotinate in Aquo-DMSO System Conductometrically

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An attempt has been made to study the kinetics of alkaline hydrolysis of methyl nicotinate in mixed solvent system for the first time by an electrochemical method evaluating rate constant by correlating conductance of the reaction mixture with concentration of reactants. The study has been made in varying compositions of water-DMSO solvent system of varying compositions (0-60% DMSO, v/v) at temperature range 20-35°. The rates were found to increase with increasing percentage of DMSO at all the temperatures. The isocomposition activation energy (E_{expt}) and the thermodynamic activation parameters were evaluated. Both ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were found to increase with the increase in DMSO content indicating solvation changes. The reaction is basically entropy-controlled. As the reaction is ion-dipole type, the increase in rate with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium shows the inadequacy of dielectric constant in explaining reaction rates as the sole parameter.

ALKALINE hydrolysis of a large number of esters have been studied in water-DMSO mixtures and the rate enhancement has been observed by many workers¹ with the increasing ratio of DMSO. According to the theory of Hughes and Ingold² as well as the theoretical predictions of Laidler and Landskröner³, the rates of such reactions should decrease with the decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. But according to the theory of Parker⁴ and subsequently supported by Roberts⁵, the rate of such reactions in which the transition state passes through large polarisation, should be faster in aprotic solvents than in protic solvents. As such more investigations are needed to arrive at a definite conclusion. It was with this view that the present study was taken since not much attention has been given to the effect of aprotic solvent on the hydrolysis of heterocyclic acid esters.

Experimental

Conductance method was used for the determining rate constant, and for this an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge with conductivity cell was used. This method has been successfully employed to study the kinetics of such reactions which occur with a change in the number or kind of ions present so that electrical conductance changes as the reaction progresses. In the present hydrolysis, the faster hydroxyl ions are replaced by slow nicotinate ions

resulting in progressive decrease in the conductance of the reaction mixture. This was recorded with time and from this the rate constant was determined by suitably correlating the conductance of the reaction mixture with the concentration of the reactants.

Correlation of conductance with concentrations: The reaction follows B_{AC}^2 mechanism,

when Δ_0 = initial conductivity before addition of the ester to the alkali (molar concn. of alkali a), Δ_t = conductivity at time t (min) when x g-mol of the ester has been hydrolysed, and Δ_∞ = conductivity when the ester has been completely hydrolysed, then

$$\Delta_0 = \lambda_M + a(\lambda_{\text{Na}^+} + \lambda_{\text{OH}^-}) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta_t = \lambda_M + (a-x)\lambda_{\text{OH}^-} + x\lambda_{\text{RCOO}^-} + a\lambda_{\text{Na}^+} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta_\infty = \lambda_M + a(\lambda_{\text{RCOO}^-} + \lambda_{\text{Na}^+}) \quad (4)$$

where λ_M is the conductance of the medium λ 's are the respective ionic conductances. From equations (2) and (3), it can be shown that

$$x = (\Delta_0 - \Delta_t) / (\lambda_{\text{OH}^-} - \lambda_{\text{RCOO}^-}) \quad (5)$$

Similarly from equations (3) and (4), it follows that

$$(a-x) = (\Delta_t - \Delta_\infty) / (\lambda_{\text{OH}^-} - \lambda_{\text{RCOO}^-}) \quad (6)$$

For a second order reaction having concentration of both the reactant molecules same,

$$K = \frac{1}{t} \frac{x}{a(a-x)} \quad (7)$$

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Putting values of x and $(a-x)$ from equations (5) and (6),

$$K = \frac{1}{at} \cdot \frac{(\Delta_0 - \Delta_t)}{(\Delta_t - \Delta_\infty)} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{or } (\Delta_t - \Delta_\infty) = \frac{1}{ak} \cdot \frac{(\Delta_0 - \Delta_t)}{t} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{or } \Delta_t = \Delta_\infty + \frac{1}{ak} \cdot \frac{(\Delta_0 - \Delta_t)}{t} \quad (10)$$

For applying equation (10), equimolar amounts of ester and alkali were used. A 0.05 N solution of the ester and a 0.05 N NaOH solution were used. Methyl nicotinate and DMSO (both E. Merck), while DMSO was purified by the reported methods⁶. Conductivity water was used in the experiments. In one set of experiment, the NaOH solution (1 ml) was diluted to 10 ml with conductivity water and organic co-solvent so that it reached the desired solvent composition. The mixture was thermostated ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) and its conductivity was determined (Δ_0). In the other set of experiment, the required amount of organic co-solvent, conductivity water and ester solution were added making the total volume 10 ml and having the same solvent composition as while determining Δ_0 . The ester solution was added in the last and conductivity of the reaction mixture was determined after suitable intervals of time (Δ_t). A plot of Δ_t against $(\Delta_0 - \Delta_t)/t$ for each solvent composition gave straight lines and from the slopes the k values were calculated.

Results and Discussion

The specific rate constants at various compositions of aquo-DMSO mixtures at different temperatures are given in Table 1. It is apparent that k value increases with the increase in DMSO content in the solvent mixture at all the temperatures. The effect of solvent composition on the rate of

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT VALUES (k) FOR THE ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL NICOTINATE IN AQUO-DMSO MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

% DMSO (v/v)	k ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)			
	20°	25°	30°	35°
0	28.7	30.1	38.2	47.9
5	26.5	33.3	43.3	53.7
10	28.8	37.2	49.4	61.0
15	33.3	42.7	54.9	72.4
20	37.5	50.0	65.3	83.0
25	42.7	55.1	72.4	97.7
30	45.7	62.2	83.2	111.0
40	54.9	77.6	108.0	148.3
50	73.3	106.4	153.1	217.8
60	101.2	158.5	239.9	354.8

hydrolysis, however, is exhibited in a better way by plotting rate constant against mole percent of DMSO in the solvent mixture (Fig. 1). Although the rate increases for all the solvent compositions but this increase slows down when the DMSO content increases beyond 8.8 mole percent in the solvent mixture. Similar changes have been observed

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log k$ vs mole percent of DMSO.

by Singh *et al.*⁷. The variation in rate with the increasing percentage of organic co-solvent in the solvent mixture is thus due to two types of operative factors—the one effective in increasing the rate and the other tending to decrease it. Upto 8.8 mole percent of DMSO, the first factor is effective and beyond 8.8 mole percent of DMSO both the factors become operative but the rate-enhancing factor predominates. The likely cause for enhancement in rate may be solute-solvent interaction and solvent-solvent interaction resulting in solvation changes both in the initial state as well as the transition state. DMSO when added to water as co-solvent has strong tendency to breakdown the water-structure as pointed out by Packer and Tomlinson⁸. Naturally the breakdown of water cluster is likely to bring about solvation changes both in initial and transition states. So far the slowing down of the increase in rate after 8.8 mole percent of DMSO in the reaction medium is concerned, it may be due to decrease in the bulk dielectric constant when DMSO content increases in the solvent mixture. The transition state is polar in nature due to the association of the catalysing base (OH^-) with one ester molecule. Formation of such polar species will be disfavoured when the dielectric constant of the medium decreases.

Both isocomposition activation energy, E_{expt} and different thermodynamic activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and G^\ddagger were calculated using appropriate method (Table 2).

The increase in E_{expt} values with the increase of DMSO content in the reaction mixture shows that it has destabilising effect due to desolvation. Moreover, desolvation will make the species more free and labile leading to increase in entropy as observed. DMSO is a poor anion solvator and is likely to desolvate the OH^- present in the initial state as well as the transition state anion. However, the bulky ester molecule in the initial state is likely

TABLE 2—VALUES OF E_{expt} , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger AND ΔG^\ddagger FOR ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL NICOTINATE IN WATER-DMSO MIXTURES

% DMSO (v/v)	E_{expt} kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)			
				20°	25°	30°	35°
0	35.70	32.34	-143.22	74.34	75.18	75.60	76.44
5	36.12	33.60	-137.34	73.92	74.76	75.18	76.02
10	38.22	35.70	-129.36	73.92	74.34	75.18	75.60
15	39.90	36.96	-124.32	73.50	74.34	74.76	75.60
20	41.16	38.64	-118.44	73.08	73.92	74.34	74.76
25	42.84	40.32	-111.72	73.08	73.50	73.92	74.76
30	45.36	42.84	-102.06	72.66	73.08	73.92	74.34
40	49.98	47.88	- 83.58	72.24	72.66	73.08	73.50
50	53.76	52.50	- 65.10	71.40	71.82	72.24	72.66
60	62.16	58.80	- 41.16	70.56	70.98	70.98	71.40

to get solvated by DMSO due to dipole-dipole interaction. Hence the potential energy of the initial state shall remain more or less unaffected, but the potential energy of the transition state will increase thereby increasing the overall energy of the system.

The increase in rate when the E_{expt} is also increasing may seem somewhat intriguing but increasing ΔS^\ddagger appears responsible for the increase in rate. DMSO is a poor anion solvator since the positive end is buried in a hydrocarbon environment and is poorly accessible to anions, $\text{CH}_3 - \overset{\delta+}{\text{S}}(=\overset{\delta-}{\text{O}}) - \text{CH}_3$. The lack of solvation of OH^- in DMSO makes it a better nucleophile and increases its reactivity.

The same conclusion can be drawn from thermodynamic considerations also. Increase in ΔH^\ddagger indicates progressive destabilisation of the activated complex on being transferred from the aqueous system to aquo-DMSO. This should have resulted in decrease in the rate, but the increase in ΔS^\ddagger at all compositions of aquo-DMSO mixture tilts the balance in favour of the reaction.

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